

Supplementary Information

Non-Invasive Therapeutic Drug Monitoring: LC-MS Validation for Lamotrigine Quantification in Dried Blood Spot and Oral Fluid/Saliva

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The method was originally developed for the analysis of six antiepileptic drugs. The multistep gradient elution was designed to ensure sufficient retention of levetiracetam, as well as adequate resolution of LTG, lacosamide, eslicarbazepine, and carbamazepine. Precisely, solvent A was ultrapure water containing 0.1% FA and solvent B was ACN containing 0.1% FA and the gradient elution started from 5 % solvent B up to 90 % solvent B in a multistep manner. Briefly, for the first three minutes, ACN reached 30 %, then stayed constant for 1 minute and then increased linearly to 90 % solvent B over the next 6 minutes. A washout phase at 90 % solvent B was maintained for 1.5 minutes before returning to 5 % for 0.5 minutes, followed by a 3-minute equilibration period.

Optimal chromatographic conditions were achieved at a column temperature of 35 °C and a flow rate of 0.45 mL/min. These parameters provided acceptable peak resolution, minimized endogenous or matrix interferences, and ensured sufficient separation for both matrices (DBS and oral fluid). The relevant EIC of each antiepileptic drug is available in Fig S1.

Figure S1 LC-MS separation of six antiepileptic drugs to examine the resolution which is evident from extracted ion chromatograms of predefined analytes. LEV-levetiracetam, LTG-lamotrigine, LCS-lacosamide, CNB-cenobamate, ESLI-eslicarbazepine, CBZ-carbamazepine. Analyte concentration was at the level of fourth concentration point in oral fluid.